

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Biodiversity Risk"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Ben Balmford

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Biodiversity Risk"[\[1\]](#). To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Anonymous evaluation 1](#)
2. [Anonymous evaluation 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice."

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5):¹ On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#).) *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Anonymous evaluator 1	65	4.0
Anonymous evaluator 2	61	3.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).²

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.³

Evaluation summaries**Anonymous evaluation 1**

The paper evaluates whether biodiversity risk is priced in asset markets and breaks new ground in doing so. It concludes that biodiversity risk is priced and provides open-source metrics for measuring biodiversity risk based on media reporting and firm-level biodiversity risk exposure based on 10K reports. The paper's strength

is that it uses primary data that is well-documented and offers it for further research. One important weakness is that both the statistical and economic significance of the result are not sufficiently discussed.

Anonymous evaluation 2⁴

This paper seeks to measure biodiversity risk. It does so in several ways:

- Via a news based measure
- textual analysis of corporate disclosures
- a survey of finance professionals, regulators and academics

The authors then apply their measures in an asset pricing and portfolio context and find that markets are pricing biodiversity risk to some degree but their survey respondents believe that market pricing of biodiversity risk is incomplete.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2		
	Anonymous			Anonymous		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁵	65	(50, 80)		61	(51, 72)	See my review
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁶	70	(60, 80)		45	(39, 50)	See my review
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁷	70	(60, 85)	8	45	(40, 50)	See my review

Logic & communication 9	81	(70, 91)	10	68	(60, 75)	See my review
Open, collaborative, replicable 11	90	(70, 100)	12	90	(80, 100)	13
Real-world relevance 14	71	(59, 80)	15	63	(55, 70)	Very good
Relevance to global priorities 16	92	(85, 100)	17	86	(75, 100)	Highly topical issues

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous		Evaluator 2 Anonymous		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	4.0	(3.5, 4.5)	3.5	(3.1, 4.0)	18

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work will be published in?	4.5	(4.0, 5.0)	4.4	(3.3, 5.0)	19
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Evaluation manager's discussion

"Biodiversity Risk" clearly adds to our understanding of the impact of Environment Social and Governance concerns on financial returns, with a focus on the emerging area of risks owing to changes in biodiversity. Moreover, it offers a novel measure of perceived biodiversity risk which can be used by future studies, perhaps in some form of shift-share (/Bartik) instrument approach.

While this paper offers novel insight, there are a few areas in which it could be improved, or more explicitly recognise its shortcomings. As both evaluations highlight, it is somewhat ambiguous as to what the paper is identifying as biodiversity risk. First, both evaluations highlight that the measure of biodiversity risk is perceptions, rather than on-the-ground changes in biodiversity risk. Indeed, large changes in actual biodiversity risk - at least physical risk - in such timeframes seem somewhat unlikely. Second, both evaluations (and particularly the second) mention the concern that measured biodiversity risk may well be picking up climate risk, and that this could be more comprehensively explored in the paper. Third, evaluation 2 highlights that nuance could be added to the discussion by disentangling physical and transition risks.

Personally, I wonder to what extent the lack of nuance in defining biodiversity risk per se within the paper is in part limited by the dictionary approach that is currently being used, which I think could well result in overly broad definitions of what constitutes biodiversity risk. If this overly broad classification is orthogonal to other factors, then the noise introduced would "only" result in estimates biased towards zero. However, there may be confounding effects introduced if those biodiversity-related terms are being used in different contexts at systematically different rates (i.e. disproportionately by a particular subset of firms or sectors).

Finally, both evaluations suggest to me that the policy implications of this research could be better explored. For instance, what does this research suggest would be required within the financial sector in order to see better

pricing of biodiversity risks? Is that even possible within financial sector regulation, or is regulation on the actual firms and their damages required? Indeed, it seems that more could be discussed within the paper about the externality regarding which firms/sectors are *exposed* to biodiversity risk, versus which are responsible for *damages* to biodiversity and increasing biodiversity risks. Similarly more could be said about the different timeframes over which damages to, and the negative impacts of, biodiversity risk are likely to occur, and the potential implications of this.

Unjournal Process

How we chose the evaluators

We looked for evaluators with:

1. Expertise in text analysis.
2. Expertise in measuring company performance indicators.

References

1. Giglio, S., Kuchler, T., Stroebel, J., & Zeng, X. (2023). Biodiversity Risk. NBER Working Paper 31137. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31137> Preprint: SocArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/n7pbj>

Footnotes

1. See "1 Mar 2024 note" above. ↵
2. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵
3. See "1 Mar 2024 note" above. See [here](#) to learn how this changed, and to see the earlier instructions. ↵
4. A previous release accidentally noted Ben Balmford as the evaluator in some of the statistics tables. Ben was an evaluation manager for this paper; he was not an evaluator. ↵

5.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

↵

6.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↔

7. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ↔

8. The authors did a good job of providing several analyses. Also, it is appreciated that the authors adjust for multiple testing. However, the lack of reporting of confidence intervals and standard errors weakens the robustness of the results. ↔

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ↔

10. The paper presents a good analysis of the perception of biodiversity risk in equity markets. However, the methodology introduced in the paper is not always easy to follow for readers unfamiliar with the topic, as it omits a short, simple explanation at the beginning and covers several aspects simultaneously. ↔

11.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

↔

12. The authors should be commended for providing the exposure measures and news index on their website. However, the authors fail to mention how the sample of firms was created, and do not provide sample statistics. Such an omission makes replication nearly impossible. ↔

13. excellent - replicability should be high ↔

14.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

↔

15. On one hand, practitioners can benefit from using the firm-level exposure measures. The authors also explain how certain industries are exposed to biodiversity risk. On the other hand, policy makers have little to gain from the paper, as the question of whether the risk pricing is adequate is not addressed. [↵](#)
16. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)
17. The paper addresses a topic that is of global relevance. [↵](#)
18. Should make it in a marginal A or B journal. [↵](#)
19. Authors are prominent in prominent institutions. [↵](#)

References

1. Giglio, S., Kuchler, T., Stroebel, J., & Zeng, X. (2023). *Biodiversity Risk*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31137> [↵](#)